

20NRM04 MetrIAQ

D2: Guideline for the use of the ERM for the improvement of the QA/QC of the emission chamber test method in EN 16516, including a description of (i) the optimal storage conditions, (ii) loading into the emission test chambers and (iii) a sampling and measurement protocol

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1 Introduction

In industrialised countries more than 80 % of the time is spent indoors. Products, such as building materials and furniture, emit volatile organic compounds (VOCs), which are therefore ubiquitous in indoor air [1]. Different VOC combinations may, under certain environmental and occupational conditions, result in reported sensory irritation and health complaints [2-6]. A healthy indoor environment can be achieved by controlling the sources and by eliminating or limiting the release of harmful substances into the air. One way is to use materials proven to be low emitting. Meanwhile, a worldwide network of professional commercial and non-commercial laboratories performing emission tests for the evaluation of products for interior use has been established. Therefore, comparability and metrological traceability of test results shall be ensured. A laboratory's proficiency can be proven by internal and external validation measures that both include the application of suitable reference materials. The emission test chamber procedure according to EN 16516 comprises several steps from sample preparation to sampling of test chamber air and chromatographic analysis [7]. Quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC) shall therefore be ensured. Currently, there is a lack of suitable reference products containing components relevant for the health-related evaluation of building products.

The European Metrology Programme for Innovation and Research (EMPIR) project *Metrology for the determination of emissions of dangerous substances from building materials into indoor air* (20NRM04 MetrIAQ) aims to develop 1) gaseous primary reference materials (gPRMs) and gaseous certified reference materials (gCRMs) and 2) emission reference materials (ERMs).

In this guideline, we want to present recommendations for the sample handling, sampling, analysis, data interpretation and evaluation of ERMs developed within the MetrIAQ project for the emission test chamber procedure. The ERMs described in this guideline are either impregnated porous materials produced by BAM, or μ -capsules filled with VOC produced by Fraunhofer IMM. Different VOCs (i.e., *n*-hexane, toluene, 2-ethyl-1-hexanol and D-limonene) were used to produce the ERMs. The performance of the ERMs was extensively tested during development, in an internal validation and additionally with help of an inter-laboratory comparison. Feedback from the inter-laboratory comparison was particularly helpful to identify possible pitfalls.

2 Overview of the emission reference materials

2.1 Generation of impregnated porous materials

The impregnation of porous materials for the generation of emission reference materials (ERMs) is conducted in an autoclave. A portion of porous material and liquid VOC are placed inside the metal vessel, which is then sealed. Gaseous CO₂ is introduced until a certain pressure is reached. The autoclave is heated up to 32 °C. Due to the increase in temperature, the pressure rises accordingly to about 74 bar where CO₂ reaches its supercritical state and acts as a solvent for the VOC. The mixture inside the autoclave is stirred and the porous material is impregnated for a few minutes. Then the pressure and/or temperature is slowly reduced. The impregnated material can be removed from the autoclave and transferred into an emission test chamber for testing. ERMs in the form of impregnated porous materials are often provided as granulates or powders. They are usually transported in air-tight containers.

2.2 Generation of μ -capsules

The VOC loaded capsules were prepared by a polyaddition/polycondensation reaction performed at the oil-in-water (O/W) emulsion droplet's interface. The process is schematically shown in **Figure 1**. The droplets were generated using a Shirasu porous glass (SPG) membrane emulsification module (External Pressure Micro Kit (MG-20), SPG Technology Co. Ltd, Japan). The hydrophilic SPG membrane with the pore size of 9.9 μm was used for the emulsification. The final average size of capsules was 60 $\mu\text{m} \pm 10 \mu\text{m}$ and the shell thickness was about 0.9 μm . The dispersed phase, consisting of 4.03 g limonene, 0.334 g tolylene-2,4-diisocyanate and 0.167 g TUBASSIST®FIX 157W was pressed through the membrane using nitrogen pressure. The droplets were formed at the pore openings on the surface of the membrane that was in contact with the continuous phase. The continuous phase consists of 120 mL surfactant(s) aqueous solution (1.2 g of polyvinyl alcohol and 0.24 g of sodium dodecyl sulphate). After all the organic phase was dispersed, the emulsion was placed in a heated oil bath at 40 °C and 5.5 ml of 6.25 wt% 1,6-hexanediamine aqueous solution was added dropwise. A reaction proceeded overnight under magnetic stirring at 300 rpm and polymerisation occurs at the droplets' interface, resulting in a μ -capsule filled with VOC. After synthesis, the capsules were washed three times with ultra-pure water to remove the excess of surfactants. Afterwards, a defined amount of the aqueous μ -capsule suspension was put into glass petri dishes and subsequently pre-aged. After complete water evaporation, a ready-to-use ERM is obtained. These ready-to-use petri dishes were distributed in air-tight packages.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of VOC encapsulation through interfacial polyaddition/polycondensation reaction.

2.3 Reference values

The VOC specific reference value and its uncertainty are provided by the distributor or the producer of the ERMs. The specific reference value can either be determined by an internal validation of the producer (or a contract laboratory) or by external validation(s) (inter-laboratory comparisons) as the mean value under consideration of the variability of the reported values. The unit of the VOC specific reference value is typically $\text{ng/g}\times\text{h}$ (emission rate). The emission rate can be translated into a VOC specific chamber air concentration with help of **equation 1.2** (chapter 4).

3 Guideline

The ERMs described in this document are intended for the use as a reference material in the emission test chamber procedure according to EN 16516. Chamber properties, chamber handling, sampling and the analytical method are described in EN 16516 and shall be followed, when using the ERMs and this guideline. Only ERM specific instructions, and, on rare occasions, recommendations to known pitfalls are given in this guideline.

3.1 Emission testing of emission reference materials

3.1.1 Sample handling and storage stability

The ERMs are usually distributed in air-tight packages (**Figure 2, E**). These packages can be stored up to 12 months at room temperature (see **Annex 3** for more information). Temporal variations in temperature between $-18\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and $35\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, which might occur during transport, will not affect the stability.

Figure 2. Examples of a μ -capsule sample (**A**) and impregnated porous materials: BEA zeolite (**B**) and C 40/4 (**C**). A typical air-tight package (**E**) is depicted. Usually, the μ -capsule sample is packed into an additional air-tight package inside of the bigger package.

One type of ERM is impregnated porous material. This can be a granulate or powder, which is packed into amber glass vials inside of the packages. When the emission test chamber is ready for testing according to the requirements defined in EN 16516, the package is opened and the desired amount of materials from the glass vials transferred into individual petri dishes. The amount of needed material can be calculated with help of **equation 1.3** in chapter 4. If powders are used, it is advised to avoid electrostatic charge (i.e., do not use gloves, try to ground yourself before handling, etc.) and to carefully flatten the surface of the powder in the petri dish (**Figure 2, B and C**). The amount of applied material is weighed with a sufficient accuracy. Any deviation will adversely affect the results.

Another, smaller air-tight, package is contained in the bigger package. It contains the pre-aged and ready-to-use μ -capsule ERM in a glass petri dish (**Figure 2, A**). The package shall be opened, and the lid of the petri dish be removed. Now all petri dishes (without lids!) can be placed into the emission test chamber.

The emission testing should be conducted for several days or weeks. The ERM distributor will provide information about the reference value, and after how many days it is obtained. It might be, that the distributor will provide several options (e.g., reference value X_1 at day 7, [...], reference value X_n at day 28) for the same material. However, better results (i.e., smaller uncertainties) will be always

obtained for longer testing durations. Former experiments showed very good results for a duration of 28 days.

3.1.2 Sampling

In general, the sampling can be conducted as described in EN 16516. However, we want to emphasise, that the sampling volume is critical and should be chosen carefully according to the expected chamber concentration **and** the calibration range. The estimated concentration can be calculated with help of **equation 1.2** or **1.3**. At least two samplings with different volumes and a sampling flow of 80–200 mL/min are recommended. It is best practice to use pumps with a calibrated internal mass flow controller/meter or in conjunction with a calibrated external mass flow controller/meter to obtain highly accurate sampling volumes.

3.1.3 Analysis

EN 16516 states, that thermal desorption gas chromatography mass spectrometry (TD-GC-MS) shall be used for the analysis of the loaded thermal desorption tubes. Depending on the scope of testing, other analytical methods can be used, such as thermal desorption gas chromatography flame ionisation detection (TD-GC-FID).

As stated in EN 16516, special attention should be given to regularly check the performance of the analytical system. We recommend using a quality control chart (i.e., regular analysis of a quality control standard including the target compounds of the ERMs), which can help to detect unregular behaviour. A quality control chart can also be used to estimate the VOC specific measurement uncertainty.

3.1.4 Sampling and measurement protocol

An example of a sampling and measurement protocol is given in **Annex 4**. It is recommended to transparently document all necessary information. This includes, but is not limited to, information about the chamber size and air exchange rate, the date/time of loading, mass of the used ERM, the reference value of the used ERM, date/time of sampling, sampling volume, analysis results (i.e., VOC specific mass on tube), calibrated range, blank values, and information about the uncertainty. The advantage of providing both, the VOC specific mass on the tube and the calibrated range, is the possibility to retrace any mismatch.

4 Evaluation of performance

The overall objective of testing a reference material is a comparison of the laboratory's result to the reference value. Different conclusions can be drawn from

this comparison. The measured value can be directly or indirectly compared. The analysis yields VOC specific masses of the analysed thermal desorption tube (m_{VOC}). This VOC specific mass is divided by the respective sampling volume ($V_{sampling}$), resulting in a VOC specific chamber concentration (c_{VOC}). Due to the use of many different chamber sizes, the concentration is often further translated into the emission rate (ER_{VOC} ; **Equation 1.1**) under consideration of the used mass of the ERM in the test chamber (m_{ERM}).

$$ER_{VOC} \left[\frac{\mu g}{h \times g} \right] = \frac{c_{VOC} \left[\frac{\mu g}{m^3} \right] \times \text{air exchange rate} \left[\frac{m^3}{h} \right]}{m_{ERM} [g]} \quad \text{Eq. 1.1}$$

Equation 1.2 can be used to calculate the expected chamber concentration (c_{VOC}) when using an ERM with a given emission rate (ER_{VOC}) and used mass of the ERM in the test chamber (m_{ERM}).

$$c_{VOC} \left[\frac{\mu g}{h \times g} \right] = \frac{ER_{VOC} \left[\frac{\mu g}{h \times g} \right] \times m_{ERM} [g]}{\text{air exchange rate} \left[\frac{m^3}{h} \right]} \quad \text{Eq. 1.2}$$

Equation 1.3 can be used to calculate needed the mass of the ERM in the test chamber (m_{ERM}) when using an ERM with a given emission rate (ER_{VOC}) in combination with the desired chamber concentration (c_{VOC})

$$m_{ERM} [g] = \frac{c_{VOC} \left[\frac{\mu g}{m^3} \right] \times \text{air exchange rate} \left[\frac{m^3}{h} \right]}{ER_{VOC} \left[\frac{\mu g}{h \times g} \right]} \quad \text{Eq. 1.3}$$

The ER normalises the concentration on the air exchange rate of the used chamber and the mass of the used ERM (m_{ERM}). This way, experiments of the same ERM conducted in different chambers and with different ERM in-weights can be compared to each other.

The comparison of a laboratory's ERM measurement result (i.e., the ER_{VOC}) to the reference value ($ER_{ERM, VOC}$) of the same ERM and VOC, can lead to either accordance or discordance. Both the values and their uncertainties need to be considered (**Equation 2**). Usually, the uncertainty ($U_{ER, VOC}$) is multiplied with a coverage factor k ($k = 2$) to obtain an enhanced uncertainty ($U_{ER, VOC}$) with a probability of $\sim 95\%$. Accordance is achieved when there is an overlap between both distributions, and discordance when there is no overlap.

$$ER_{VOC} \pm U_{ER, VOC} \leftrightarrow ER_{ERM, VOC} \pm U_{ERM, VOC} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

4.1 ERMs used for internal verification

As it can be seen in **chapter 4**, a laboratory needs to determine the ER_{VOC} and estimate its uncertainty. This includes the measurement uncertainty of the analysis, the uncertainty of the sampling and the uncertainty of the emission test chamber.

The deviation between the measured $ER_{VOC} \pm U_{ER, VOC}$ and the reference value $ER_{ERM, VOC} \pm U_{ERM, VOC}$ is an indication of the performance of the laboratory. The closer this deviation is to the typical standard deviation of the test method, the better is the performance of the laboratory.

However, the performance could be further evaluated based on the laboratory's uncertainty (i.e., the lower the uncertainty the better; is it comparable to the uncertainty of the ERM or to the uncertainty of other professional laboratories?). An in-depth uncertainty evaluation (e.g., with help of the bottom-up approach) might show potential for improvement. A list of uncertainty sources can be found in the D5 report of this project. In case of accordance with only little overlap, the laboratory should consider investigating their equipment, calibration, and methodologies. In case of discordance, the laboratory is strongly advised to investigate all the above-mentioned.

4.2 ERMs used for inter-laboratory comparisons

Valuable information can also be obtained by participating in an inter-laboratory comparison. A comparison between the laboratory's value and the reference value is conducted and a laboratory can compare itself to other laboratories. A rough estimate of the emission test chamber procedure's uncertainty for the tested target compounds of the ERM can be calculated based on the standard deviation of the values reported by the laboratories ($s_{ref, VOC}$).

The evaluation of performance is usually based on the z score, but others, such as the zeta or E_n score are also possible according to ISO 13528 [8]. The reference value ($ER_{ref, VOC}$) can be pre-determined or assigned during the inter-laboratory comparison. It can be calculated as the mean value of the reported values of the participants or as the mean value of only a group of participants (e.g., experienced laboratories). The z score of a laboratory ($Z_{lab, VOC}$) is calculated as the difference of the laboratory's value and the reference value, divided by the standard deviation of the reference (**Equation 3**).

$$Z_{lab, VOC} = \frac{ER_{lab, VOC} - ER_{ref, VOC}}{s_{ref, VOC}} \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

ISO/IEC 17043 [9] proposes the interpretation of the z score as follows:

$|z| \leq 2$ satisfactory result

$2 < |z| < 3$ questionable result

$|z| \geq 3$ unsatisfactory result

Similar to **chapter 4.1**, a laboratory needs to evaluate their performance based on the z score and the estimated uncertainties. In-depth investigations of the equipment, calibration, and methodologies can be advised or necessary.

Annex 1 Internal validation

The internal validation was conducted from May 2023 to May 2024. A set of ERMs was produced at BAM and Fraunhofer IMM and distributed between the consortium partners BAM and Eurofins. Batches of impregnated AC C 40/4 (VOC: *n*-hexane; granulate), AC C 45/4 (VOC: toluene; granulate), AC C 40/4 (VOC: 2-ethyl-1-hexanol; granulate) and μ -capsules (VOC: D-limonene; capsule type HDTTL) were produced. The batches of impregnated porous materials were split into smaller portions and filled into amber glass vials. Many petri dishes were filled with exactly 1.357 mL of aqueous μ -capsule suspension and pre-aged in an emission test chamber (\sim 2 weeks, 23 °C, 0 % rel. humidity). Air-tight packages containing each material with a specific mass/number of petri dishes were prepared based on the chamber size of the two partners and the emission rate of the ERMs (**Table 3**). The goal was to achieve a target concentration between 50–150 ng/L for each VOC. The packages were stored for different times and temperatures (**Table 1**) to investigate the storage stability of the ERMs. Six samples were measured immediately after arrival at BAM and one sample at Eurofins to obtain values for the in-batch repeatability and to have a value without influence of the storage conditions. After the given storage time has passed, the respective package was left to reach room temperature, opened, and the impregnated porous materials from the vials were transferred into individual petri dishes. Then all petri dishes (3 petri dishes with impregnated porous materials and 1 petri dish with pre-aged μ -capsules) were placed into an emission test chamber.

Table 1. Storage conditions and number of packages.

Storage time [months]	Temperature [°C]	Comment
immediate testing (IT) after arrival	-	6 packages for BAM, 1 package for Eurofins
0.5	-18	1 package for each partner
0.5	5	1 package for each partner
0.5	23	1 package for each partner
0.5	35	1 package for each partner
1	5	1 package for each partner
1	23	1 package for each partner
1	35	1 package for each partner
3	5	1 package for each partner
3	23	1 package for each partner
6	5	1 package for each partner
6	23	1 package for each partner
12	5	1 package for each partner
12	23	1 package for each partner

Samples were taken exactly after 24 h (1 day), 72 h (3 days), 168 h (7 days), 240 h (10 days), 336 h (14 days), 504 h (21 days) and 672 h (28 days). Two different

volumes (BAM: 1 and 2 L; Eurofins: 2.3 L and 5 L) were sampled into Tenax[®] TA tubes each time. The sampling rate was between 45–87 mL/min (Eurofins) or 90–110 mL/min (BAM), and either a calibrated mass flow controller and/or a calibrated mass flow meter was used to determine the exact sampling volume (**Table 4**).

A1.1 Analytical method at BAM

The sorbent tubes were analysed by a gas chromatograph (GC, 6890N, Agilent) coupled to a flame ionisation detector (FID) and equipped with a thermal desorber (TD, TDSA 2, Gerstel) with a two stages desorption. In the first stage, the sorbent tube was heated, and the desorbed VOC components were transferred and concentrated into a cold injection system (CIS, CIS 3, Gerstel) at –100 °C. The temperature programme used for the sorbent tube desorption started at 40 °C (hold 1 min) and heated with a rate of 40 °C/min to 280 °C (hold 5 min). In the second stage, after collecting the desorbed substances from the TD oven was finished, the cold trap was quickly heated with a rate of 12 °C/s to 280 °C (hold 3 min) so the compounds were released and sent to the GC column. The GC column was an RTX-Volatiles (60 m length, 0.32 mm inner diameter, 1.5 µm film thickness, Restek). A constant pressure of 1.3 bar (equals to about 2.5 mL/min flow) and He (99.9999 %, Linde) as a carrier gas were used. The effluent was introduced (splitless) into the GC column and the temperature programme of the GC started: 40 °C (hold 5 min), heated with a rate of 4 °C/min to 80 °C, then heated with a rate of 7 °C/min to 180 °C, and then heated with a rate of 10 °C/min to 260 °C (hold 4 min). The FID was operated at a temperature of 280 °C, with a flow of 35 mL/min H₂, 350 mL/min synthetic air and 42.5 mL/min He make-up gas.

The TD-GC-FID system was calibrated at the beginning and end of each month. The external calibration was performed by preparing a solution of different VOCs (*n*-hexane, toluene, D-limonene and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol) in methanol (MeOH). The solution was diluted to yield five concentrations ([20, 100, 180, 260, 340, 420] ng/µL). One µL of each calibration standard was then spiked into individual Tenax[®] TA tubes, which were then measured by the TD-GC-FID. Additionally, the second calibration standard (100 ng) was measured twice a week as a QC standard.

A1.2 Analytical method at Eurofins

The sorbent tubes were analysed by a GC (7890A, Agilent) coupled to a mass spectrometer (MS) (5977B/5975C, Agilent) and equipped with a TD (TD-100/TD100-rx, Markes) with a two stages desorption. In the first stage, the sorbent tube was heated, and the desorbed VOC components were transferred and concentrated into a cold trap cooled at 10 °C. The temperature used for the sorbent

tube desorption was 300 °C (hold 7 min). In the second stage, after collecting the desorbed substances from the TD oven was finished, the cold trap was quickly heated to 300 °C (hold 3 min) so the compounds were released and sent to the GC column. The GC column was a HP-5MS (30 m length, 0.25 mm inner diameter, 0.25 µm film thickness, Agilent). A constant column flow of 1 mL/min and He (99.9999 %, Linde) as a carrier gas were used. The effluent was introduced with a split of 1:50 into the GC column and the temperature programme of the GC started: 45 °C (hold 4 min), heated with a rate of 15 °C/min to 300 °C. The MS was operated with an ion source temperature of 250 °C and a quadrupole temperature of 180 °C.

All detected components were calculated from relative response factors (RRFs) against toluene's response. Before samples were run on the instrument, a set of standards were run (liquid solutions spiked on Tenax® TA tubes) and evaluated to gauge the performance and response of the instrument. The lowest calibration standard was 5 ng.

Annex 2 Parameters and results of the internal validation

A2.1 Chamber sizes

The used chamber sizes of partners during the internal validation are given in **Table 2**.

Table 2. Chamber sizes of the partners conducting the internal validation.

Partner (int. validation)	Chamber size [L]	Air exchange rate [h ⁻¹]
BAM	270	0.5
Eurofins	119	0.5

A2.2 Sample in-weights

The sample in-weights of the ERMs used in the internal and external validation are given in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Sample in-weights of ERMs for the internal and external validation.

Partner (int. validation)	Material	VOC	m [g] per package
BAM	C 40/4 (granulate)	n-hexane	~0.446 ^a
	C 45/4 (granulate)	toluene	~0.441 ^a
	C 40/4 (granulate)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	~0.963 ^a
	µ-capsules	D-limonene	2 petri dishes ^b

Eurofins	C 40/4 (granulate)	n-hexane	~0.217 ^a
	C 45/4 (granulate)	toluene	~0.214 ^a
	C 40/4 (granulate)	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	~0.431 ^a
	μ-capsules	D-limonene	1 petri dish ^b

^a Average value per package. Accurate values were used for the interpretation and calculation. ^b One petri dish contains 1.357 mL aqueous μ-capsule suspension with 6.8 w% capsules.

A2.3 Sampling volumes

The sampling volumes of the internal validation are given in **Table 4**. Since the data interpretation focuses on the last day of the emission testing (day 28), only volumes from these days are given.

Table 4. Sampling volumes of the ERM emission tests of the internal validation. Only the sampling volume after 672 h (28 days) is given.

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	V1 [L]	V2 [L]	V1 [L]	V2 [L]
IT 1	1.259	1.993	2.156	5.363
IT 2	0.996	1.978	-	-
IT 3	0.992	1.985	-	-
IT 4	0.998	1.992	-	-
IT 5	0.990	1.985	-	-
IT 6	0.998	1.993	-	-
-18°14d	0.990	1.985	2.200	5.190
5°14d	0.996	1.978	2.225	5.190
23°14d	0.990	1.987	2.225	5.160
35°14d	0.998	1.992	2.225	5.190
5°1m	0.969	1.991	2.327	5.251
23°1m	0.999	2.667 ^a	2.225	5.040
35°1m	0.996	1.985	2.444	5.370
5°3m	0.952	1.992	2.300	5.040
23°3m	0.950	1.967	2.150	5.418
5°6m	0.933	1.979	2.250	5.133
23°6m	0.871	1.982	2.300	5.190
5°12m	0.921	1.800	2.200	5.133
23°12m	0.901	1.829	2.652	5.246

^a Not a reliable value – pump behaviour irregular.

A2.4 Measurement results

The measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by TD-GC-FID or TD-GC-MS) are given in **Table 5** (*n*-hexane), **Table 6** (toluene), **Table 7** (2-

ethyl-1-hexanol) and **Table 8** (D-limonene). Only results of day 28 (672 h after loading the ERMs into the emission test chamber) are given.

Table 5. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by TD-GC-FID or TD-GC-MS) of the internal validation (VOC = n-hexane); sampled on day 28.

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]
IT 1	97.88	156.22	168.00	158.00
IT 2	52.92	102.11	-	-
IT 3	76.80	154.74	-	-
IT 4	73.60	142.48	-	-
IT 5	86.15	175.59	-	-
IT 6	84.51	165.57	-	-
-18°14d	49.86	100.35	133.00	214.00
5°14d	62.57	132.28	244.00	448.00
23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	93.00	74.00
35°14d	64.02	129.29	238.00	382.00
5°1m	86.48	185.56	113.00	176.00
23°1m	51.52	100.05	247.00	459.00
35°1m	114.40	188.57	131.00	245.00
5°3m	59.77	124.17	- ^a	461.00
23°3m	63.02	127.75	185.00	340.00
5°6m	53.38	125.83	132.00	259.00
23°6m	51.64	127.73	231.00	360.00
5°12m	61.07	126.35	192.00	315.00
23°12m	49.61	99.70	124.00	158.00

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available.

Table 6. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by TD-GC-FID or TD-GC-MS) of the internal validation (VOC = toluene); sampled on day 28.

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]
IT 1	151.97	251.20	239.00	286.00
IT 2	105.01	230.12	-	-
IT 3	109.03	241.87	-	-
IT 4	107.96	231.77	-	-
IT 5	122.80	258.94	-	-
IT 6	114.05	237.28	-	-
-18°14d	108.30	227.20	227.00	480.00
5°14d	103.63	229.45	261.00	550.00
23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	110.00	100.00
35°14d	95.53	198.59	290.00	573.00
5°1m	84.28	195.65	270.00	630.00
23°1m	49.18	99.68	301.00	680.00

35°1m	143.27	248.35	259.00	678.00
5°3m	70.08	161.38	- ^a	669.00
23°3m	76.69	160.89	306.00	698.00
5°6m	104.39	220.49	191.00	501.00
23°6m	101.14	229.10	253.00	580.00
5°12m	98.84	202.60	220.00	508.00
23°12m	98.50	199.57	299.00	527.00

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available.

Table 7. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by TD-GC-FID or TD-GC-MS) of the internal validation (VOC = 2-ethyl-1-hexanol); sampled on day 28.

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]
IT 1	255.02	413.81	252.00	338.00
IT 2	216.67	450.09	-	-
IT 3	219.10	474.57	-	-
IT 4	169.10	372.56	-	-
IT 5	203.06	429.22	-	-
IT 6	133.34	282.43	-	-
-18°14d	158.52	341.83	305.00	573.00
5°14d	103.63	229.45	278.00	522.00
23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	110.00	65.00
35°14d	155.58	323.34	292.00	464.00
5°1m	156.73	378.37	593.00	1160.00
23°1m	63.83	140.94	389.00	775.00
35°1m	178.43	318.75	347.00	869.00
5°3m	117.99	258.77	- ^a	943.00
23°3m	91.51	208.67	177.00	502.00
5°6m	172.62	356.15	273.00	608.00
23°6m	181.88	421.19	415.00	759.00
5°12m	147.92	295.77	196.00	391.00
23°12m	206.84	398.35	703.00	960.00

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available.

Table 8. Measurement results (mass on the respective tube, measured by TD-GC-FID or TD-GC-MS) of the internal validation (VOC = D-limonene); sampled on day 28.

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]	m1 [ng]	m2 [ng]
IT 1	19.67	31.85	53.70	71.50
IT 2	16.26	33.05	-	-
IT 3	15.79	33.47	-	-
IT 4	14.85	31.59	-	-
IT 5	16.97	35.88	-	-
IT 6	18.68	38.13	-	-

-18°14d	13.09	27.34	33.90	92.80
5°14d	12.18	25.22	28.00	87.50
23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	16.00	21.00
35°14d	23.64	48.30	72.10	178.00
5°1m	8.46 ^b	20.34	70.30	97.40
23°1m	18.13	38.06	62.70	125.00
35°1m	17.11	30.80	58.60	81.10
5°3m	3.35 ^b	14.14	- ^a	89.70
23°3m	1.33 ^b	9.91 ^b	32.20	77.10
5°6m	20.81	36.57	70.40	75.50
23°6m	10.00 ^b	13.73	17.20	26.50
5°12m	13.02	21.78	26.60	57.60
23°12m	5.16 ^b	6.10 ^b	3.85 ^b	5.93

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available. ^b Below lowest calibration standard.

A2.5 Calculated emission rates of the internal validation

The measurement results of the internal validation were translated into emission rates (*ER*) according to the **Equation 1** in chapter 4. The *ERs* are given in **Table 9** (*n*-hexane), **Table 10** (toluene), **Table 11** (2-ethyl-1-hexanol) and **Table 12** (D-limonene). Only results of day 28 (672 h after loading the ERMs into the emission test chamber) are given.

Table 9. Emission rates of the internal validation calculated based on the information given above (VOC = *n*-hexane).

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]
IT 1	24.90	25.10	22.37	8.46
IT 2	17.81	17.30	-	-
IT 3	25.44	25.62	-	-
IT 4	23.50	22.78	-	-
IT 5	27.03	27.46	-	-
IT 6	25.81	25.30	-	-
-18°14d	15.88	15.94	16.60	11.32
5°14d	19.67	20.93	31.23	24.59
23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	12.17	4.18
35°14d	19.96	20.20	30.82	21.21
5°1m	28.30	29.54	14.43	9.96
23°1m	15.99	11.63	28.23	23.16
35°1m	34.45	28.49	15.66	13.33
5°3m	19.44	19.30	- ^a	26.56
23°3m	20.96	20.52	24.32	17.74
5°6m	18.02	20.03	17.37	14.94

23°6m	18.31	19.90	27.26	18.83
5°12m	20.30	21.48	23.89	16.80
23°12m	17.45	17.28	8.61	5.54

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available.

Table 10. Emission rates of the internal validation calculated based on the information given above (VOC = toluene).

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]
IT 1	37.60	39.26	33.03	15.89
IT 2	34.93	38.54	-	-
IT 3	36.59	40.58	-	-
IT 4	35.02	37.64	-	-
IT 5	37.11	39.01	-	-
IT 6	36.21	37.70	-	-
-18°14d	33.63	35.18	28.08	25.17
5°14d	31.47	35.07	33.46	30.23
23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	13.76	5.39
35°14d	29.53	30.76	35.90	30.41
5°1m	26.56	30.00	31.03	32.08
23°1m	14.98	11.37	34.49	34.39
35°1m	42.56	37.02	29.29	34.89
5°3m	23.15	25.47	- ^a	39.16
23°3m	24.77	25.10	40.02	36.23
5°6m	35.08	34.94	19.60	22.54
23°6m	35.33	35.17	31.73	32.23
5°12m	32.39	33.95	26.83	26.55
23°12m	34.74	34.69	32.90	29.31

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available.

Table 11. Emission rates of the internal validation calculated based on the information given above (VOC = 2-ethyl-1-hexanol).

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]
IT 1	29.75	30.49	16.14	8.70
IT 2	33.49	35.03	-	-
IT 3	32.68	35.38	-	-
IT 4	24.93	27.51	-	-
IT 5	29.15	30.72	-	-
IT 6	19.45	20.62	-	-
-18°14d	23.14	24.87	19.40	15.45
5°14d	18.17	19.49	17.50	14.09

23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	7.00	1.78
35°14d	22.35	23.28	18.43	12.55
5°1m	23.65	27.77	34.23	29.68
23°1m	9.05	7.48	24.31	21.38
35°1m	25.42	22.79	18.98	21.63
5°3m	17.72	18.57	- ^a	26.16
23°3m	13.88	15.28	11.39	12.82
5°6m	26.58	25.86	16.10	15.72
23°6m	30.00	30.53	24.27	19.67
5°12m	23.26	23.78	12.05	10.30
23°12m	33.19	31.50	36.77	25.39

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available.

Table 12. Emission rates of the internal validation calculated based on the information given above (VOC = D-limonene).

Storage conditions	BAM		Eurofins	
	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]	ER1 [µg/h×g]	ER2 [µg/h×g]
IT 1	11.85	12.12	16.06	8.60
IT 2	13.10	13.40	-	-
IT 3	12.42	13.16	-	-
IT 4	11.46	12.20	-	-
IT 5	12.64	13.32	-	-
IT 6	14.21	14.51	-	-
-18°14d	9.89	10.30	9.94	11.53
5°14d	9.15	9.54	8.11	10.87
23°14d	- ^a	- ^a	4.64	2.62
35°14d	17.71	18.13	20.89	22.11
5°1m	6.62	7.75	19.48	11.96
23°1m	13.38	10.52	18.17	15.99
35°1m	12.57	11.35	15.46	9.74
5°3m	2.64	5.31	- ^a	11.48
23°3m	1.05	3.77	9.66	9.18
5°6m	16.68	13.82	20.18	9.48
23°6m	8.59	5.18	4.82	3.29
5°12m	10.57	9.05	7.80	7.24
23°12m	4.28	2.50	0.94	0.73

^a Gross error during measurement, no value available.

Annex 3: Data interpretation of the internal validation

The data of the internal validation was used to determine different values for repeatability, reproducibility and storage stability of the ERMs.

A3.1 Sample homogeneity (in-batch repeatability)

During internal validation, six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel at BAM. The results are correlated in a sense, that many usually variable parameters were basically the same, such as ambient air pressure, performance of the measurement device or temperature in the laboratory. This reduced the variability of the results to only a few remaining parameters, such as the homogeneity of the materials (**Table 13**). Very good homogeneities were found for the toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample. Mediocre homogeneities were found for the *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples.

Table 13. Results of the in-batch repeatability test. Six replicates of the same ERM batches were measured in parallel. The toluene impregnated C 45/4 (granulate) and the D-limonene loaded μ -capsule sample are highly homogenous. The *n*-hexane and 2-ethyl-1-hexanol impregnated C 40/4 (granulate) samples revealed only mediocre homogeneities.

	n-hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonen
average ER [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\cdot\text{g}$]	24.0	36.2	28.2	13.1
standard deviation [$\mu\text{g}/\text{h}\cdot\text{g}$]	3.5	1.1	5.3	0.9
rel. SD [%]	14.5	3.0	18.6	6.7

A3.2 Reproducibility and short and long-term stability of the ERMs

Furthermore, a reproducibility and a short and long-term stability study were conducted with the same materials. Air-tight packages were distributed to Eurofins and BAM and stored for different times and at different temperatures. No trend was found for any of the storage conditions. High and low values were obtained for short and long storage times (0, 0.5, 1, 3, 6 and 12 months), as well as for each temperature (-18, 5, 23 and 35 °C) (**Figure 3**).

BAM and Eurofins; n-hexane

BAM and Eurofins; toluene

BAM and Eurofins; 2-ethyl-1-hexanol

Figure 3. VOC specific emission rates (ER) of BAM and Eurofins for samples stored under different storage conditions. No trend was observed for any storage time or temperature. A gross measurement error occurred at BAM's measurement of the '23°14d' sample.

Since the storage does not seem to have any influence, we used the same results to calculate the in-batch reproducibility (**Table 14**). The testings were conducted at two different laboratories and over 12 months, so it kind of resembles the top-down approach. This way, the reproducibility reveals the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure. Both partners produced very similar average emission rates and relative standard deviations.

Table 14. Results of the in-batch reproducibility (values taken from the investigation of storage conditions). The results of BAM and Eurofins are very similar. The relative standard deviation can be used as a measure for the variability of the overall emission test chamber procedure.

	<i>n</i> -hexane	toluene	2-ethyl-1-hexanol	D-limonen
mean ER [µg/h×g] BAM	21.5	31.2	23.0	9.5
mean ER [µg/h×g] Eurofins	22.4	30.4	19.9	13.2
mean ER [µg/h×g] both	21.9	30.8	21.4	11.4
standard deviation [µg/h×g] BAM	5.1	7.0	6.6	4.3
standard deviation [µg/h×g] Eurofins	6.5	7.1	7.0	5.8
standard deviation [µg/h×g] both	5.7	6.9	6.7	5.3

rel. SD [%] BAM	23.9	22.3	28.5	44.8
rel. SD [%] Eurofins	28.9	23.2	35.1	44.2
rel. SD [%] both	26.2	22.4	31.4	47.0

A3.3 Batch-to-batch repeatability

A batch-to-batch repeatability can be concluded from experiments conducted during the development of the impregnated porous materials at BAM (no value available for the μ -capsules). Unfortunately, a batch-to-batch reproducibility was not yet conducted. But since Eurofins and BAM had very similar values during the internal validation (**Table 14**), it can be assumed, that a repeatability conducted over a prolonged time span is comparable to the reproducibility.

The batch-to-batch repeatability is dependent on the ERM (i.e., material and VOC combination). Values are given in **Table 15**. In general, the repeatability is not very good. The best batch-to-batch repeatability was found for BEA.

Table 15. Batch-to-batch repeatability of a variety of ERMs. The repeatability is given as relative standard deviation.

ERM / granules, powders and μ -capsules	Batch-to-batch repeatability of the ER 14 days after loading [%]	Batch-to-batch repeatability of the ER 21 days after loading [%]
C 40/4 [n-hexane]	18	12
C 40/4 [toluene]	39	21
C 40/4 [2-ethyl-1-hexanol]	15	11
C 45/4 [n-hexane]	18	11
C 45/4 [toluene]	28	13
C 45/4 [2-ethyl-1-hexanol]	-	-
BEA [n-hexane]	9	6
BEA [toluene]	12	8
BEA [2-ethyl-1-hexanol]	12	7
μ -capsules HDTTL [D-limonene]	-	-

Annex 4: Example of a sampling and measurement protocol

Laboratory Name:

Author:

ERM reference value [$\mu\text{g}/\text{g}\cdot\text{h}$]:

Used amount of ERM in test chamber [g]:

Date of ERM delivery:

Date / time of chamber loading:

Sampling #	1	2	3	4	5
Sample name					
Date / time					
Sampling Volume [L]					
m(VOC ₁) [ng]					
m(VOC ₂) [ng]					
m(VOC ₃) [ng]					
m(VOC ₄) [ng]					
m(VOC ₅) [ng]					
m(VOC ₆) [ng]					
m(VOC ₇) [ng]					
m(VOC ₈) [ng]					
m(VOC ₉) [ng]					
m(VOC ₁₀) [ng]					
Comment					

Instrumentation^a:

Calibration^a: calibrated range, method and/or quality control measures

Sampling^a:

Uncertainty^a:

Data processing^a: e.g. calculation of emission rate (ER)

Blank values:

Results: end results (e.g., $ER_{\text{VOC},1}$, $ER_{\text{VOC},x}$, ...) \pm uncertainty for each value

Other categories: e.g. location of data, chamber data (size, air flow etc.)

^a reference to standard operating procedures is possible (when for internal use), or to EN 16516 if for the purpose sufficient.

Conclusions

The validation exercise has identified suitable reservoir materials that can be used as reference materials for emissions:

1. Capsule types containing limonene were obtained that are usable under the standardised test conditions prescribed in EN 16516. Depending on the best suited shell material (GTIL1 and HDTTL_143), stable emission profiles within 5-10 % decrease over 14 days were achieved. The knowledge obtained here is a good basis for the development of further encapsulated VOC for which the shell composition must be individually chosen.
2. The impregnated activated carbon did not show such a good stability in terms of the emission profile in humidified air but by applying the numerical model from objective 4 (refer to deliverable D4 of this project) the emission profile can be well described so that these materials would be good suited for e.g., round robin tests. For dry air applications at least two porous materials (FD-107 and 13X APG) provide stable emission profiles in terms of the project goals.

Both the aims of objective 1 regarding the development of usable ERMs and objective 3 regarding their internal validation were fully achieved.

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